

EFFECT OF THE MORPHOLOGY ON FRACTURE TOUGHNESS OF THERMOPLASTIC/THERMOSET/CLAY HYBRID NANOCOMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

Unsaturated polyester resins (UPRs) are thermosetting polymers with high crosslink density which leads to superior properties for them. On the other hand, it results in their brittleness. In order to improve their fracture toughness, incorporation of an inclusion is a common method. The inclusion can promote energy dissipating processes during crack propagation such as localized plastic deformation of the matrix, matrix void formation, cavitation of soft inclusions (e.g. rubbers), and particle/matrix debonding. In addition, the inclusion located in the front of the crack tip can perturb crack front during propagation. Perturbation of crack front leads to crack deflection and/or crack bowing (pinning) resulting in an increase in fracture toughness [1].

Rubber toughening is used as a common technique to improve fracture toughness of thermosets. The rubbery dispersed phase can result in a significant improvement in fracture toughness but at the cost of Young's modulus, compressive strength, and thermal stability [2]. Thermoplastic additives and nano-reinforcements also can be used for this purpose without the expense of other properties, but they are not as effective as rubber additives [2].

In addition, combinations of nanoclay and other additives have a synergistic effect to improve toughness [3-5]. Therefore, these ternary systems have attracted a lot of interest. Recently, we introduced novel thermoplastic/thermosetting hybrid nanocomposites as a ternary system to improve fracture toughness of unsaturated polyester [5]. The technique led to a substantial improvement in fracture toughness without sacrificing other properties.

In the presence of a secondary phase, the morphology of the system plays important roles to determine fracture toughness and the mechanisms controlling fracture toughness [5,6]. However, a few studies have been done into the morphology of ternary systems [4,6,7]. In the case of UPRs,

thermoplastic additives have been widely used as low profile additives to control volume shrinkage instead of toughening agents [8,9]. To the author's knowledge, there is no study on fracture toughness of thermoplastic/clay/unsaturated polyester ternary systems; most investigations have looked at the effect of thermoplastic/clay combination on volume shrinkage. In addition, in our previous work, we found that the particle size had significant influence on fracture toughness emphasizing the importance of the system microstructure. In this work, the effect of the morphology on fracture toughness of our hybrid nanocomposite systems was investigated.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

Cloisite 20A (Southern clay products Inc.) was used as the nanoclay. Methyl methacrylate and styrene (Sigma Aldrich) were distilled prior using an IKA rotary evaporator under vacuum at 30 °C to remove the inhibitors. Benzoyl peroxide (Sigma Aldrich) was used as a thermal initiator for the thermoplastic synthesis and the room temperature initiator employed for curing the whole system was methyl ethyl ketone peroxide (NOROX, MEKP-925H from NORAC Inc.). The unsaturated polyester resin (H596-CWA-12, Ashland chemical), is a general purpose orthophthalic resin synthesized from maleic anhydride, phthalic anhydride, and propylene glycol. It contains 45wt% of styrene and 0.1wt% cobalt octoate promoter.

In this work we consider 3 different classes of materials: (1) simple polyesters (SP) which contain unsaturated polyester and one or two crosslinking agents; (2) simple nanocomposites (SN) which contain Cloisite 20A in addition to the components of class 1; (3) hybrid nanocomposites (HN) which contain the thermoplastic additive (copolymer of methyl methacrylate and styrene, P(MMA/S)) in addition to the components of class 2. In the name of samples, the first number refers to the molar ratio

of MMA/St as curing agents and the second number refers to clay loading in phr unit.

2.2 In situ polymerization of thermoplastic additive

The mixture of clay and vinylene monomers (MMA and styrene) was prepared as follows. First, dried clay (6.3 phr based on the weight of vinylene monomers) was mixed with the raw reactants at 1000 rpm for 1h at room temperature, followed by high shear mixing at 7500 rpm for 15 minutes, slow mixing at 500 rpm for 30 minutes, and then another 15 minutes at 7500 rpm. The copolymerization of MMA and styrene was initiated by adding 0.2 mol% of BPO, based on the mole of vinylene monomers, and carried out at 65°C under reflux in a nitrogen atmosphere while mixing at 300 rpm.

2.3 Hybrid polyester and nanocomposite preparation

The resin was mechanically mixed with the reaction products from in situ polymerization at 1000 rpm for 3h. MEKP (1wt % based on the weight of the UP/St/MMA system) was added and the mixture was mixed for further 2 min under vacuum to remove air bubbles. The mixture was poured into molds, cured at room temperature for 12 h and post-cured at 110°C for 4h. In order to represent the relative amount of MMA and styrene present to act as curing agents we use the molar ratio (M/S). A ratio of 0.0 indicates that only styrene is present for curing. Simple nanocomposites were prepared by the direct mixing process. The clay was gradually added to the resin and mixed for 8h at 2000 rpm. The mixture was cast and cured following the same procedure as above.

2.4 Characterization Methods

Calorimetry was performed with a differential scanning calorimeter TA Q10 on 10mg of uncured sample in a hermetic aluminum pan. The isothermal reaction rate profile was measured at 25°C, followed by a scan from 25-300°C at a heating rate of 5°C/min to determine the total reaction heat.

X-ray diffraction analyses were performed using an X-ray diffractometer (Philips model X'PER) at the low angle range of 2θ with a scanning speed of 1 °/min. The X-ray source was Cu-K α radiation ($\lambda=1.54 \text{ \AA}$), using a 50 kV voltage generator and a 40 mA current. The nanostructure of nanocomposite samples were also examined with transmission

electron microscopy (TEM) using a JEOL JEM-2100F microscope operating at a 200kV accelerating voltage. The samples were cut into thin sections (50-80 nm thickness) using an ultramicrotome with diamond knife.

Dumb-bell shaped specimens based on ASTM D638-82a (type V) were used to determine tensile properties on an Instron 3365 (5 kN) testing machine at a constant crosshead speed of 1mm/min. Fracture mechanic tests were carried out by MTS 312.21 (100 kN) according to ASTM D5045-99 on sharply notched three-point bend specimens at a constant crosshead speed of 10 mm/min.

A Hitachi S-4700 FE-SEM 2 kV scanning electron microscope was used to observe the fracture surface. The microstructure study was done by using an optical microscope (Variscope). A polishing procedure according to ASTM (E2015-4) was used for preparation of the optical microscopy sample.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Micro and nanostructure

X-ray diffraction patterns and transmission electron microscopy (TEM) showed a fine intercalated/exfoliated structure for hybrid nanocomposites [5]. Based on optical microscopy (Figure 1), hybrid samples exhibited particulate morphology with thermoplastic-rich domains dispersed throughout the continuous thermoset-rich phase.

Fig.1. An optical micrograph of a polished surface of hybrid sample HN/0.2/2phr.

TEM verified that the majority of silicate layers are located inside the thermoplastic-rich domains [5]. In addition, inside the domains, there are thermoset

microgels in spherical shapes which are surrounded by several tactoids of clay. Therefore, domains consist of thermoplastic as the continuous phase and thermoset microgels dispersed throughout the thermoplastic. Hence, these domains are considered as thermoplastic-rich phase. Figure 2 shows a TEM image representing the nanostructure of a thermoplastic-rich domain in a hybrid sample.

Fig.2. A TEM image from hybrid sample HN/0.2/2phr representing nanostructure of a thermoplastic-rich domain

3.2 Matrix characteristics

In our previous work [5], we found that a parameter which significantly influences the microstructure of the system is clay loading resulting in a change in fracture toughness. In addition, clay may affect toughness by altering matrix characteristics although the majority of silicate layers are located inside the thermoplastic-rich domains. Two characteristics of the matrix affect fracture toughness are: (i) crosslink density and (ii) yielding.

The key parameter changing crosslink density of the matrix is the molar ratio of curing agents. During mixing procedure, different constituents, especially MMA and styrene, diffuse into the thermoplastic-rich droplets. The presence of clay inside the particles affects their diffusion rate resulting in a change in the molar ratio of the curing agents (MMA/St) in the continuous phase. Consequently,

the matrix characteristics may be changed by the addition of clay. Therefore, a series of experiments were designed to find out the effect of (MMA/St) molar ratio on the characteristics of unsaturated polyester in a simple system without the clay and thermoplastic.

Glass transition temperature is a suitable criterion which directly depends upon crosslink density of the thermoset in these simple systems. Figure 3 shows the T_g of simple polyester samples with different molar ratios of MMA/St (0.0, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, and 0.8). The data show the low amount of MMA up to the molar ratio of 0.4 slightly increased the T_g indicating a minor increase in crosslink density. In contrast, the higher molar ratio resulted in a significant reduction in the T_g indicating a decrease in crosslink density. Therefore, we chose a variation range of 0.1 to 0.4 for the molar ratio of the curing agents to avoid changing in crosslink density of the matrix.

Tensile strength is also reflecting crosslink density of the thermoset. Table 1 presents mechanical properties of the simple polyesters. The addition of MMA resulted in an increase in tensile strength compared to neat UPR (SP/0.0) indicating a slight increase in crosslink density which is also confirmed by the T_g results. In the presence of MMA, tensile strength of all simple polyesters containing different amount of MMA is the same, suggesting this variation range of the second curing agent ($0.1 < \text{MMA/St} < 0.4$) does not change crosslink density (Figure 4).

Fig.3. Effect of MMA content on glass transition temperature of simple polyesters

The addition of MMA caused a slight increase in tensile modulus compared to the neat polyester system. In the presence of MMA, the modulus of all samples with different MMA contents are almost the

same suggesting that the compactness of the network in the systems is not affected by MMA content in this range of variation.

The other characteristic of the matrix affecting fracture toughness is its localized yielding which requires cooperative chain motion and local mobility. It strongly depends on the chemical structure of the network; therefore, the molar ratio of the curing agents may affect it. A criterion to evaluate localized yielding of the matrix is inelastic strength where its lower value refers to higher capability of the matrix for localized plastic deformation around the tip of the propagating crack. The stress at the onset of inelastic behavior (inelastic strength, σ_i) is calculated by using 0.2% offset strain criterion.

Fig.4. Effect of MMA content on tensile strength and inelastic strength of simple polyesters

Figure 4 indicates that the presence of MMA in the network caused a slight reduction of inelastic strength compared to neat polyester (SP/0.0) suggesting an increase in the potential of the network for localized yielding. However, in the presence of the second curing agent, different MMA contents resulted in the same value of σ_i .

Table 1 indicates that the presence of MMA in the network resulted in a slight improvement in fracture toughness (K_{Ic}). In a brittle polymer, the mechanisms may control fracture toughness are crazing and localized shear yielding (micro-shear band formation). In a highly crosslinked thermoset system, crazing can not occur since the formation of fibrils of the craze structure is severely restricted by chemical crosslinks between the polymer molecules. Therefore, the only mechanism is localized shear yielding. The observed improvement in fracture toughness is due to the effect of MMA on localized plastic deformation of the matrix in the vicinity of the crack tip.

During crack propagation, there is a concentrated stress in the vicinity of the crack tip which can exceed yield strength of the polymer leading to shear band formation. This localized yielding leads to the formation of a plastic zone around the crack tip. In the case of thermosets, since the major energy dissipating process is matrix plastic deformation, we can estimate the plastic zone size in the crack tip based on Irwin model where the equation for plane strain condition is [10]:

$$r_y = \frac{1}{6\pi} \left(\frac{K_{Ic}}{\sigma_y} \right)^2 \quad (1)$$

where r_y , K_{Ic} , and σ_y are the radius of the plastic zone around the crack tip, critical stress intensity factor, and tensile yield strength respectively. The values of r_y for different simple polyester samples were presented in Table 1. The presence of MMA in the network structure resulted in an increase in the size of plastic zone around the crack tip indicating higher energy dissipation during crack propagation which resulted in the observed improvement in fracture toughness.

The addition of MMA as the second curing agent caused a slight increase in both characteristics of the thermoset, but different ratios of MMA/St led to the same results. Therefore, the matrix characteristics do not play important role in controlling fracture toughness in this variation range.

Table 2 shows mechanical properties of systems containing clay, thermoplastic or a combination of clay and thermoplastic. In general, in the presence of an inclusion in a matrix, adhesive strength of the interface between two phases play important role in tensile strength. The data indicates that the addition of the thermoplastic (HP/0.2), clay (SN/0.0/2phr), or their combination (hybrid nanocomposites, HN) caused a reduction in tensile strength due to the imperfect adhesion at the interface between the inclusion and the continuous thermoset matrix. In the hybrid nanocomposites, the addition of clay caused a reduction in tensile strength. Interfacial adhesion strength depends on the size of the particles where it is increased by a reduction in the size of the particles [11]. Table 3 presents the size (average diameter) of the thermoplastic-rich particles. The addition of clay up to 2phr slightly increased the size of the thermoplastic-rich domains resulted in a small reduction in tensile strength. In contrast, 3phr clay loading led to a significant

increase in the particle size resulted in a substantial reduction in tensile strength.

Comparison of inelastic strength of different hybrid nanocomposites indicates that matrix plasticity is not changed by clay loading confirming that the intensity of localized plastic deformation of the matrix is almost the same for all samples. The addition of clay slightly increased the modulus of the nanocomposites due to its high stiffness relative to the organic polymers. This is an advantage of this toughening technique compared to rubber toughening techniques.

3.3 Fracture toughness and mechanisms

The addition of clay (SN/0.0/2phr) slightly increased fracture toughness (Table 3) since the silicate layers make a localized tortuous path for crack propagation resulting in an increase in the fracture surface area. The thermoplastic additive (HP/0.2) makes a second phase dispersed throughout the matrix. During crack propagation, the thermoplastic-rich domains are not rigid enough to resist against crack propagation and they are fractured which can be seen in SEM images from the fracture surface of this sample (Figure 5).

Therefore, during crack propagation, plastic deformation of the thermoplastic domains occurs. This is the major energy dissipating process in this system resulting in a slight improvement in fracture toughness [5]. Also, SEM images show the occurrence of some debonding of the particle/matrix which can have a contribution to toughening via crack blunting.

In hybrid nanocomposites (HN/0.2), the presence of clay inside the thermoplastic-rich domains increases impenetrability of the particles. In this case, the thermoplastic-rich domains can perturb the crack front during propagation. SEM images (Figure 6) of the fracture surface of one hybrid nanocomposite (HN/0.2/2phr) show that the majority of the thermoplastic-rich particles are almost intact after fracture. It suggests that these particles act like inorganic rigid particulate fillers where the main controlling mechanism is crack pinning [13]. In SEM micrographs, many thick fracture tails are visible behind the particles consistent with pinning of the crack front [12].

Table 1. Tensile properties and K_{Ic} of simple polyesters with different MMA contents

Sample	Tensile strength (MPa)	Tensile modulus (GPa)	Inelastic strength (MPa)	K_{Ic} (MPa. m ^{1/2})	r_y (μm)
SP/0.0	61.5 (3.0) ^a	3.34 (0.06)	36.8 (0.6)	1.15 (0.09)	51.7
SP/0.1	70.5 (1.8)	3.53 (0.03)	32.3 (0.6)	1.33 (0.07)	90.6
SP/0.2	70.6 (2.3)	3.56 (0.04)	31.9 (0.2)	1.32 (0.06)	90.7
SP/0.3	71.8 (2.6)	3.57 (0.06)	32.3 (0.7)	1.31 (0.08)	87.3
SP/0.4	71.2 (2.2)	3.50 (0.05)	31.5 (0.5)	1.28 (0.05)	87.7

a: The values in parentheses are standard deviations of the property from 7 samples

Table 2. Tensile properties of different systems

Sample	Tensile strength (MPa)	Tensile modulus (GPa)	Inelastic strength (MPa)
SP/0.0	61.5 (3.0) ^c	3.35 (0.06)	36.8 (0.6)
SN/0.0/2phr ^a	57.7 (1.3)	3.42 (0.06)	32.6 (0.5)
HP/0.2 ^b	57.3 (3.2)	3.52 (0.06)	31.0 (0.5)
HN/0.2/1phr ^b	56.9 (1.9)	3.35 (0.04)	28.8 (0.7)
HN/0.2/2phr ^b	52.9 (1.3)	3.41 (0.04)	29.06 (0.9)
HN/0.2/3phr ^b	42.7 (1.5)	3.40 (0.06)	27.5 (1.5)

a: Simple nanocomposite without thermoplastic

b: All hybrid systems contain 7wt% the thermoplastic

c: The values in parentheses are standard deviations of the property from 7 samples.

Table.3. K_{Ic} and r/c of different samples

Sample	Particle Diameter (2r) (μm)	Interparticle distance (c) (μm)	r/c	K_{Ic} ($\text{Mpa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$)
HP/0.2	3.40 (1.4)	9.02 (2.7)	0.19	1.42 (0.05)
HN/0.2/1phr ^c	4.10 (0.9)	8.23 (4.2)	0.25	1.52 (0.08)
HN/0.2/2phr ^c	5.35 (0.7)	9.09 (4.6)	0.29	1.83 (0.06)
HN/0.2/3phr ^c	10.48 (3.5)	14.27 (10.3)	0.37	1.59 (0.07)

a: All samples contain 7wt% thermoplastic

b: The values in parentheses are standard deviations of the property

c: All hybrid nanocomposites contain 7wt% the thermoplastic

(a)

(a)

(b)

(b)

Fig.5. SEM images of fracture surface from sample HP/0.2 with two magnifications. The arrow indicates direction of fracture.

Fig.6. SEM images of fracture surface from sample HN/0.2/2phr with two magnifications. The arrow indicates direction of fracture.

Although the major mechanism controlling the fracture toughness in hybrid nanocomposite systems is crack pinning, debonding of the particles from the matrix (breakdown of the particle/matrix interface)

is also likely. This leads to a reduction in the effectiveness of crack pinning, but results in crack tip blunting and unstable propagation which can increase the fracture toughness [13].

Table 3 indicates that 2 phr clay is the optimum content of clay in the hybrid nanocomposite systems to improve fracture toughness. For crack pinning, impenetrability of the inclusions is important. Probably, lower clay loading (1 phr) does not contribute enough rigidity to the thermoplastic-rich domains to perturb crack front during propagation. Therefore, crack pinning can not completely occur resulting in lower fracture toughness. On the other hand, higher clay loading (3 phr) resulted in lower fracture toughness which is likely related to the microstructure.

3.4 Effect of the microstructure

In crack pinning mechanism, in addition of impenetrability of the inclusions, their size and interparticle distance influence fracture toughness. In the previous work [5], we found that clay affects the size of the thermoplastic-rich domains. Therefore, in this work, three clay loading (1, 2, and 3phr) were applied to evaluate the clay effect on both the size and distribution of the thermoplastic-rich domains.

Table 3 shows an increase in the size of the thermoplastic-rich particles by the addition of clay. To interpret the clay effect, the microstructure development in these systems must be understood. During mixing of the unsaturated polyester resin with the thermoplastic/clay mixture, small droplets of the thermoplastic mixture are formed. Small molecules of curing agents (MMA and styrene) can diffuse into the droplets faster than unsaturated polyester (UP) molecules. Consequently, these droplets are first swollen by curing agents monomers. This swelling phenomenon makes more opportunity for UP molecules to diffuse into the droplets. Therefore, these thermoplastic-rich droplets contain all constituents. The presence of exfoliated clay inside the droplets causes an increase in their viscosity. Higher viscosity of the droplets compared to that of the continuous phase leads to an increase in the resistance of the droplets against shear stress during mixing. As a result, the size of the droplets attained during the mixing and will be higher when clay is present [5]. In addition, the presence of silicate layers restricts the mobility of unsaturated polyester molecules to diffuse out of the droplets during phase separation resulting in an increase in the particle size. The final size of the droplets after curing will then depend on the size of the dispersed phase before solidification, the rates of diffusion of constituents in and out of the thermoplastic-rich phase under quiescent conditions.

According to crack pinning mechanism, the growing crack is pinned by the particles causing the crack front to bow out between the particles. Therefore, toughening results from the particles impeding crack propagation. After bowing, crack keeps propagating and after a distance of about one particle diameter, the crack front breaks free and again it makes a line shape [14]. In this case, two distances become important to control toughening which are: (i) the interparticle distance and (ii) the distance that the crack propagates along the particles before breaking free which is called critical propagation distance. The former one is linked to the particle concentration and diameter. Fracture toughness is increased when the interparticle distance decreases and the critical propagation distance increases [14]. Therefore, distribution of particles plays an important role in fracture toughness. Table 3 presents the interparticle distance and its standard deviation, which represents the non-uniformity degree of interparticle distance, in samples containing different clay loading. Clay loading up to 2phr did not significantly change the interparticle distance and heterogeneity of particle distribution. In contrast, higher clay loading (3phr) led to a sudden increase in the interparticle distance and its standard deviation referring to non-uniform distribution of the thermoplastic-rich domains. It means some areas are free of particles whereas dense aggregations of particles exist in other spots. Consequently, the sample with higher clay loading (3phr) has lower fracture toughness compared to the sample with uniform distribution of the particles (2 phr clay loading).

Different theories have been proposed to predict the effect of these parameters on toughening such as Evans' model [13]. He suggested a correlation between the ratio of the particle size, radius (r), to interparticle distance (c) and K_{Ic} . His model predicts an increase in fracture toughness by increasing r/c . In some cases, a maximum in the relationship between toughness and the volume fraction of inclusions, which affects r and c , was reported which can not be predicted by Evans' model. Rose [15] suggested an alternative analysis which is in better agreement with the experimental observations. An increase in the particle size increases fracture toughness, however there is an optimum interparticle distance for each specific particle size. In our system, the addition of clay caused the increase in the particle size, but fracture toughness of the sample containing 3phr is reduced in spite of containing the biggest particles. Heterogeneity of

particle distribution in this sample caused the reduction in fracture toughness by decreasing the portion of crack front perturbed by the particles. In all crack pinning models, the effect of heterogeneity of particle distribution was not considered whereas uniform and regular distribution of the particles was assumed. However, our results show that particle distribution significantly influences fracture toughness which calls for more investigation.

In addition, other material variables must be evaluated while they have the minimum effect on other factors affecting fracture toughness, such as the matrix characteristics and penetrability of the particles, but at the same time, they change the size and distribution of the particles. In that case, a correlation between microstructure characteristics and fracture toughness can be found.

4. Conclusion

Clay affected fracture toughness by changing the microstructure and fracture mechanism without a significant effect on crosslink density and localized yielding of the thermoset matrix. The presence of clay in the thermoplastic-rich domains influences the impenetrability, size, and distribution of the particles which are significantly important in crack pinning mechanism. The lower clay content (1 phr) was not enough to increase impenetrability of the particles for perturbing the crack front during propagation. On the other hand, the higher clay loading (3 phr) caused non-uniform distribution of particles resulted in low fracture toughness. Hence, 2 phr clay is optimum loading to promote crack pinning resulting in a significant improvement in fracture toughness.

5 References

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